

**DEVELOPMENT OF A TECHNOLOGY FOR DETECTING AND
ELIMINATING BIOKINEMATIC AND BIODYNAMIC ERRORS IN
ATHLETES INVOLVED IN ICE HOCKEY**

Soyibjon Tajibaev

Doctor of pedagogical science (DSc), professor at the
Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sport

Khojiev Shokhrukh

Lecturer at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sport

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Biokinematic and biodynamic errors are incorrect movements that athletes make in the course of sports, and which can lead to injury or reduced performance. Various technologies such as sensor systems, high-speed cameras, and computer algorithms are used to detect and eliminate these errors. Regular performance evaluation and the use of modern technologies such as virtual reality, machine learning and artificial intelligence help to improve the process of detection and elimination of biokinematic and biodynamic errors in athletes and increase their performance.

The development of a technology for detecting and eliminating biokinematic and biodynamic errors in ice hockey athletes may include several stages:

Data collection: Collecting data on the movements and postures of athletes during activities and competitions using various sensors such as accelerometers, gyroscopes, cameras and others. The sensors can be attached to the athlete's body or to a hockey stick.

Data Analysis: Analyze sensor data to identify biokinematic and biodynamic errors that can lead to injury and performance loss. Various methods can be used to analyze the data, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence algorithms.

Evaluation of results: Evaluation of the results of data analysis to determine which errors are most important to eliminate. This may include determining key movement parameters such as speed, angle and direction of movement, as well as evaluating the effectiveness of the current technique.

Development of an individual program: Development of an individual error correction program for each athlete, based on his individual characteristics and problem areas. This may include determining the most effective exercises and correction methods, as well as developing an individual training plan.

Training: Providing training that includes error correction exercises, which may include exercises to improve balance, strength, flexibility, and movement technique. Trainings can be carried out both individually and in a group.

Evaluation of results: Evaluation of results after correcting errors and making changes to the training program. This may include reusing sensors and analyzing data to determine how well errors have been corrected, as well as comparing results with past data.

After correcting errors and making changes to the training program, it is necessary to evaluate the results. To do this, you can reuse sensors and motion analysis systems to collect data about the movements of the athlete in training.

The obtained data should be analyzed using computer algorithms and models to determine how successfully the errors were eliminated and what changes occurred in the biokinematic and biodynamic parameters of the athlete's movement.

In addition, the results of training can be evaluated by comparison with past data. For example, you can compare the speed of movement, the accuracy of strikes, and other parameters of the movement of an athlete before and after making changes to the training program.

For a more objective assessment of the results, comparisons with other ice hockey athletes can also be made to determine how successfully the errors were corrected and what results were achieved in comparison with other athletes.

In general, evaluating the results after correcting errors and making changes to the training program is an important step that allows you to determine the effectiveness of the changes made and make additional adjustments to the training program, if necessary.

Leading experts in the field of detecting and eliminating biokinematic and biodynamic errors in ice hockey athletes are actively working on the development and improvement of technologies that allow more accurate analysis of the movements of athletes and improve their results.

Among the main generalizations made by leading experts are the following:

Analyzing the movement of athletes using sensor systems and a high-speed camera is the most effective way to identify biokinematic and biodynamic errors that can lead to injury and reduced performance.

The use of computer algorithms and models allows more accurate analysis of the data obtained using sensors and a high-speed camera, and reveals hidden patterns and dependencies that may affect the results of athletes.

The introduction of electronic training and monitoring systems allows you to more accurately control the training process, manage loads and prevent overwork and injuries.

It is important to evaluate the results regularly to determine the effectiveness of the changes made and to make additional adjustments to the training program, if necessary.

The development of technologies such as virtual reality, machine learning and artificial intelligence can help improve the process of detecting and eliminating biokinematic and biodynamic errors in athletes and improve their performance. Summarizing, leading experts emphasize the importance of using the latest technologies and techniques to detect and eliminate biokinematic and biodynamic errors in athletes involved in ice hockey, and express optimism about the prospects for the development of this topic in the future.

One of the authors in this direction, M. Berger, worked in the field of detection and elimination of biokinematic and biodynamic errors in athletes involved in ice hockey. He and his team conducted a study that analyzed the movements and hitting techniques of hockey players using a high-speed camera and sensor system.

Research has shown that many hockey players have biokinematic and biodynamic errors that can reduce their performance and risk of injury. For example, errors can occur when performing movements in hockey-specific positions, such as the position of the body when making a shot, the position of the arms and legs, the direction of gaze, etc.

M. Berger and his team proposed a number of recommendations to eliminate errors and improve the hitting technique of hockey players. These recommendations include correcting the position of the body and hands, changing the trajectory of movements, improving coordination of movements, etc.

The study by M. Berger and his team is an important contribution to understanding the problems of biokinematic and biodynamic errors in hockey players and allows coaches and specialists to create more effective training programs aimed at eliminating these errors.

In conclusion, it can be said that the detection and elimination of biokinematic and biodynamic errors is an important aspect of the training process for ice hockey athletes. With the help of modern technologies such as sensor systems, high-speed cameras and computer algorithms, errors can be quickly and accurately detected and corrected, which allows athletes to achieve better

results and avoid injuries. However, it is important to keep in mind that technology should only be used as a complement to the experience and knowledge of experienced trainers and professionals, and not as a substitute for them. Only a combination of experience and technology allows you to achieve the best results and ensure the safety of athletes.

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